

Thorium Peroxo Complexes catalysed Oxidation of Olefins using tert-Butyl Hydroperoxide

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There is a considerable interest in peroxo complexes of transition metals¹⁻¹⁴. This has prompted us to synthesise some peroxo complexes of thorium using bidentate, tridentate and tetradentate ligands. The catalysts though found unreactive for cyclohexene as stoichiometric reagent have been observed to be active as catalyst when anhydrous tert-butylhydroperoxide was used as oxidant.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation of cyclohexene gave cyclohexene oxide, cyclohexenone and cyclohexenol as the products. When evolution of oxidation products was followed using ThO₂ (anthranilic acid)₂/TBHP

system it was observed that upto 60 min the yield of cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone was the same (1.5% each) but with time the yield of cyclohexenone increased and after 160 min the yield of cyclohexenone was six times more than cyclohexenol. Under experimental conditions the thorium peroxo complexes were found to catalyse the oxidation of cyclohexanol to cyclohexanone. A number of thorium peroxo complexes have been used to screen their catalytic activity (Table 1) and all the complexes showed catalytic activity. Table 1 shows the results obtained after 4 h of the reaction. It was observed that if the reaction was carried out beyond 4 h, i.e. upto 12 h, the formation of epoxide was also observed in ThO₂ (SAPEN) and ThO₂

TABLE I---EPOXIDATION OF CYCLOHEXENE CATALYSED BY PEROXOTHORIUM COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Catalyst	Cyclohexene oxide mmol (%)	Yield Cyclohexenol mmol (%)	Cyclohexenone mmol (%)
1.	ThO ₂ (Anthranilic acid) ₂	0.01 (0.5)	0.008 (0.4)	0.05 (2.5)
2.	ThO ₂ (ACEN)	0.013 (0.65)	0.08 (4.05)	0.202 (10.1)
3.	ThO ₂ (SALEN)*	0.001 (0.05)	0.008 (0.4)	0.02 (1.0)
4.	ThO ₂ (SAPEN)*	Traces	0.012 (0.6)	0.04 (2.0)
5.	ThO ₂ (ANAC hydrazene) H ₂ O	0.002 (0.10)	0.014 (0.70)	0.026 (1.3)
6.	ThO ₂ (SAP) H ₂ O	0.031 (1.55)	0.014 (0.70)	0.128 (6.4)

*Higher yield than this can be obtained on prolong heating (>12 h) in presence of slightly excess TBHP.

(SALEN) catalysed reaction showing that these complexes have longer induction period. Highest yield of the epoxide was obtained with ThO₂(SAP)H₂O catalyst while highest yield of allylic oxidation products was obtained using ThO₂(ACEN) catalyst. The studies of the effect of various additives, viz. pyridine, imidazole, NaHCO₃ and NaH₂PO₄ on the oxidation of cyclohexene showed that pyridine decreased the yield of the epoxide while increasing the yield of the allylic oxidation products. Imidazole was found to inhibit completely the oxidation reaction. The addition of NaHCO₃ also decreased the yield of the epoxide. NaH₂PO₄, a weak acid, also decreased the yield of epoxide but the decrease was less compared to that found in NaHCO₃ addition. The surfactants, viz. sodium lauryl sulphate, Triton X-100 and cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide were added in order to study the effect of micelles on the epoxidation reaction. Sodium lauryl sulphate and Triton X-100 completely inhibited the epoxidation and cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide also retarded the reaction.

Oxidation of cyclo-olefins viz. cyclopentene, cyclohexene, cycloheptene, cyclooctene and norbornene using ThO₂(SAP)H₂O/TBHP system showed that the relative rate of reactivity follows the order: cyclooctene (15.75), norbornene (10.30), cyclopentene (3.64), cycloheptene (1.1), cyclohexene (1.0). Comparison of this data with that obtained using peracetic acid¹⁵ shows that the relative reactivities of cycloheptene, cyclohexene and cyclopentene follows the same order. Higher rates of epoxidation observed with norbornene, cyclooctene and cycloheptene compared to cyclohexene shows that the olefin is not coordinated to metal center during epoxidation. Had olefin been coordinated to metal center, the rate of olefins having carbon atom number higher than cyclohexene would have been lower, contrary to what was observed using ThO₂(SAP)H₂O catalyst. The rate of hydrogenation using (PPh₃)₃RhCl decreases with increasing olefin ring size as coordination of olefin to metal center takes place in the transition state¹⁶. A similar relative rate of epoxidation using O=Mo(TPP)-OMep-umene hydroperoxide¹⁷ and MoO₃(SALEN)/TBHP system¹⁸ has been observed. Here torsional strain and bond angle strain play important role in anticipating the relative reactivity of cyclic olefins.

Thorium peroxo complexes when subjected to stoichiometric epoxidation of cyclohexene, no product was observed even after 12 h of the reaction.

The observation that thorium peroxo complexes having tridentate and tetradentate ligands are active catalysts is in contrast to the findings observed in the case of zirconium peroxo⁷ and uranium peroxo¹² complexes where tri- and tetradentate ligand containing complexes have been reported to be stable. But these findings are in agreement with the results obtained using titanium peroxo complex¹³ which is inactive when used stoichiometrically but active when used as catalyst in presence of tert-butylhydroperoxide.

Mechanism: On the basis of the results obtained, the following mechanisms may be proposed for the oxidation of olefin using ThO₂(SAP)H₂O/TBHP system.

Out of these two mechanism, Scheme 1 may not be operative in the ThO₂(SAP)H₂O/TBHP system as it was observed that the catalyst on stoichiometric oxidation did not produce epoxide and allylic oxidation products even after 12 h of the reaction.

Scheme 2 is supported by the following observations. (i) The presence of induction period shows that thorium peroxo catalyst does not react directly with the substrate but it forms an intermediate species with tert-butyl hydroperoxide, which might transfer oxygen to the olefin. Further, the addition of pyridine and imidazole decreases the epoxide formation as they are strong coordinating agent thereby inhibiting the approach of tert-butyl hydroperoxide to metal center. Similar behaviour using pyridine with O=Mo(TPP)OMe/TBHP system¹⁴ has been observed. (ii) Thorium peroxo complexes

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

show catalytic activity only in presence of tert-butyl hydroperoxide. Similar behaviour has been reported with $\text{TiO}_2(\text{TPP})$ catalyst¹⁸. A long induction period has been reported. (iii) Addition of NaHCO_3 reduces substantially the yield of the epoxide. This is explained by the fact that basic nature of the additive prevents the opening of the peroxo linkage and base is also known to promote peroxo complex formation¹⁹. Addition of NaHCO_3 also reduces the yield of epoxide in $\text{O}=\text{Mo}(\text{TPP})\text{OMe}$ ¹⁴, $\text{MoO}_3(\text{SALEN})/\text{TBHP}$ ¹⁸ systems and $\text{TiO}_2(\text{TPP})/\text{TBHP}$ system¹⁸. (iv) Higher rates of epoxidation

observed with norbornene, cyclooctene and cycloheptene compared to cyclohexene shows that olefin is not coordinated to metal center during epoxidation. This observation rules out the possibility of Scheme 1 as in this scheme coordination of olefin to metal center takes place. (v) The evidences in favour of Scheme 2 also suggest that *cis*-hydroxy(alkylperoxo)thorium(IV) complex acts as the active species, a species similar to that suggested for titanium¹³ and molybdenum porphyrin¹⁴ catalysed

reactions. This is further supported by the finding that NaH_2PO_4 which has slightly acidic character also reduces the yield of the epoxide, this is because of the fact that acidic compounds which help in the opening of the epoxide ring also acts as catalyst in the formation of peroxo complex¹⁹ thereby reducing the yield of epoxide. (vi) Formation of cyclohexenone suggests that a homolytic decomposition of tert-butyl hydroperoxide results in the formation of allylic oxidation products⁹. The increase in the formations of cyclohexenone and also the oxidation of cyclohexenol to cyclohexenone, show that oxidation of secondary alcohol to carbonyl compound is taking place. This finding suggests that the *cis*-hydroxy(alkylperoxo)thorium(IV) complex undergoes homolytic fission and not heterolytic fission, thereby giving high concentration of allylic oxidation products. Similar results have been observed with chromium peroxo¹⁰, vanadium peroxo¹⁰ and CrO_3/TBHP system²⁰. The oxidation of cyclohexanol to cyclohexanone can also be explained satisfactorily by Scheme 2. (vii) The reaction of *cis*-stilbene with $\text{ThO}_2(\text{SAP})\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{TBHP}$ system gives a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-stilbene oxides. The formation of *trans*-epoxide shows that an intermediate having free radical is involved as rotation of C-C bond takes place before ring closure²¹.

The epoxidation of *trans*-stilbene give only the *trans*-epoxide. This shows that Scheme 2 is operative and homolytic cleavage of *cis*-hydroxyalkylperoxo-thorium(IV) takes place. (viii) It has been observed that when $\text{ThO}_2(\text{SAP})\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is used as catalyst in presence of 70% TBHP, the oxidation of cyclohexene give cyclohexene oxide, cyclohexenone and cyclohexenol. But the significant finding in this system is the high selectivity for cyclohexenol, and very low yield of cyclohexenone shows that oxidation of cyclohexenol to cyclohexenone is retarded. This can prove to be a effective system for the hydroxylation of alkanes and in this catalytic system water has no detrimental effect as observed with $\text{O}=\text{Mo}(\text{TPP})\text{OMe}$ and $\text{O}=\text{Ti}(\text{TPP})$ catalysts. This finding is in favour of the fact that heterolytic cleavage of the TBHP did not take place.

On the basis of aforementioned evidences, it is concluded that in the thorium peroxo complexes, first coordination of tert-butyl hydroperoxide to metal center takes place resulting in the formation of *cis*-hydroxyalkylperoxothorium(IV) species as intermediate which undergoes homolytic cleavage resul-

ting in the formation of epoxide and allylic oxidation product. The formation of appreciable amount of cyclohexenone suggests that it can be a good system for the oxidation of secondary alcohol to carbonyl compounds as well as for the hydroxylation of alkanes.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde, anthranilic acid, acetylacetone, *o*-aminophenol, ethylenediamine, propylenediamine, dodecane (all Aldrich) and 30% H_2O_2 (Glin India) were used. Tert-butyl hydroperoxide (Aldrich) was taken dry in benzene and estimated²². All the starting olefins were checked by gas chromatography and whenever needed purified by the literature procedure²³. Pyridine, imidazole, $NaHCO_3$, NaH_2PO_4 , sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTABr) and Triton X-100 were of high purity. A Nucon-Amil 5700 GC equipped with a Shimadzu CR-3A data processor and F.I.D. as detector was used. XE-60 and Carbowax-20M were used as column materials. The analysis of chromatographic samples was done at 120°. The reference samples of oxides were prepared by the literature procedure²⁴. 1H nmr spectra (90 MHz) were measured with a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer.

Thorium peroxo complexes: The thorium peroxo complexes were prepared using anthranilic acid, as bidentate ligand, salicylaldehyde-*o*-aminophenol (SAP), 2-carboxyphenylhydrazonopentan-2,4-dione (ANAC hydrazone) as tridentate ligands¹⁸, bis(salicylaldehyde)ethylenediamine (SALEN), bis(acetylacetone) ethylenediamine (ACEN), bis(salicylaldehyde)propylenediamine (SAPEN) as tetradentate ligands²⁵. The thorium peroxo complexes using anthranilic acid, was synthesised using literature procedure²⁶. The other complexes were synthesised following the typical procedure.

$Th(NO_3)_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.002 mol) in water (10 ml) was added to a solution of the ligand (0.002 mol) in methanol (25 ml). To it 30% H_2O_2 (12.5 ml) was added and the mixture was warmed on a water-bath for 30 min. The product separated was washed with water and ether and dried. The complexes were characterised using elemental analysis and spectral techniques²⁵.

Oxidation of cyclohexene: To cyclohexene (20 mmol) was added thorium peroxo complex (0.002 mmol) as catalyst, dodecane (0.2 ml) as internal standard and tert-butyl hydroperoxide (2.0 mmol) in benzene (10 ml). The contents were heated at 80° for 4 h. The unreacted hydroperoxide was then destroyed using sodium sulphite, extracted with ether and dried (anhydrous $MgSO_4$). The contents were analysed by G.C. The oxidation gave cyclohexene oxide (3.6 min), cyclohexenol (6.75 min) and cyclohexenone (11.02 min) as products.

Effect of additives: The effect of various additives, viz. pyridine, imidazole, $NaHCO_3$,

NaH_2PO_4 , sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTABr) and Triton X-100 was studied by taking cyclohexene (20 mmol), $ThO_2(SAP)H_2O$ (0.002 mmol) as catalyst, tert-butyl hydroperoxide (2.0 mmol), dodecane (0.2 ml), benzene (10 ml) and the additive (100 mg). The contents were heated under N_2 atmosphere for 4 h. The hydroperoxide was decomposed and the products were analysed by gas chromatography.

Competitive oxidation of cyclic olefins: The competitive oxidation of cyclic olefins, viz. cyclopentene, cyclohexene, cycloheptene, cyclooctene and norbornene was carried out by taking $ThO_2(SAP)H_2O$ catalyst (0.004 mmol), cyclohexene (20 mmol), dodecane (0.2 ml), other cyclic olefin (20 mmol), tert-butyl hydroperoxide (4.0 mmol) and benzene (10 ml). The contents were heated under N_2 -atmosphere at 80° for 4 h and the products were analysed. For product analysis in the oxidation of stilbenes the catalyst was removed and the nmr spectral analysis was showed *cis*-stilbene oxide (singlet 4.25) and *trans*-stilbene oxide (singlet 3.85)¹⁸.

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References

1. A. D. WESTLAND, F. HAQUE and J. M. BOUCHARD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 225.
2. D. A. MUCCIGROSSO, S. E. JACOBSON, P. A. AFGAR and F. MARES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 7083.
3. H. MIMOUN, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1980, **7**, 1.
4. A. D. WESTLAND and M. T. H. TARAFDAR, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 3228.
5. O. BARTOLINI, V. CONTE, F. DI FURIA and G. MODENA, *Nouv. J. Chim.*, 1985, **9**, 157.
6. H. MIMOUN, M. POSTED, F. CASABIANCA, J. FISCHER and A. MITSCHLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 1303.
7. M. T. H. TARAFDAR and M. A. L. MIAH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 2265.
8. M. T. H. TARAFDAR and A. R. KHAN, *Polyhedron*, 1986, **5**, 1207.
9. R. A. SHELDON and J. K. KOCHI, "Metal Catalysed Oxidation of Organic Compounds", Academic, New York, 1981.
10. H. MIMOUN in "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", ed. G. WILKINSON, 1987, Vol. 6, p. 329.
11. H. MIMOUN, M. MIGNARD, P. BRÉCHOT and D. SAUSSINE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 8711.
12. A. D. WESTLAND and M. T. H. TARAFDAR, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 3992.
13. H. J. LEDON and F. VARESCON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 2735.
14. H. J. LEDON, P. DURBUT and F. VARESCON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 3601.
15. D. SWERN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1692.
16. B. R. JAMES, "Homogeneous Hydrogenation", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1973, p. 210.
17. F. VARESCON, Thesis, L'Universite Claude Bernard, France, 1982.
18. D. D. AGARWAL, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1988, **65**.
19. M. INAMO, S. FUNAHASHI and M. TANAKA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 2475.
20. D. D. AGARWAL, S. SRIVASTAVA and P. CHADHA, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 487.

NOTES

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| <p>21. K. SRINIVASAN, P. MICHAUD and J. K. KOCHI, <i>J. Am. Chem. Soc.</i>, 1986, 108, 2309.</p> <p>22. K. B. SHARPLESS and T. R. VERHOEVEN, <i>Aldrichim. Acta</i>, 1979, 12, 63.</p> <p>23. D. D. FERRIN, W. L. ARMAREGO and D. R. FERRIN, "Purification of Laboratory Chemicals", Pergamon, New York, 1980</p> | <p>24. D. SWERN, <i>Org. React.</i>, 1953, 7, 378; L. F. FISHER and M. FISHER, "Reagent for Organic Synthesis", Wiley, New York, 1967, Vol. 1.</p> <p>25. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT and A. CHAKRAVORTY, <i>Prog. Inorg. Chem.</i>, 1966, 1, 83.</p> <p>26. M. T. H. TARAFDAR, <i>Indian J. Chem., Sect. A</i>, 1989, 26, 874.</p> <p>27. D. D. AGARWAL, S. SRIVASTAVA and P. CHADHA, <i>Polyhedron</i>, in the press.</p> |
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